

The method of preparation was, however, found unsuitable for our purpose as the starting material namely oleic acid was difficult to obtain in a sufficiently pure form and the isolation and the purification of both nor-oleic and bis-nor-oleic acid was difficult. Besides, the yields in the two intermediate oxidation operations were unsatisfactory (*vide* experimental.)

EXPERIMENTAL.

I: 1-Dimethyl- Δ^9 -octadecenol-1 (I).—A Grignard solution (4 mol.) was prepared from magnesium (32 g.) in ether (500 c.c.) and methyl iodide (100 c.c.) in ether (150 c.c.) and a solution of methyl oleate (100 g.) in ether (150 c.c.) was added to this drop by drop under ice-cooling. The reaction was not very vigorous and no precipitate of the Grignard complex separated. The mixture was kept overnight and then heated under reflux on the water-bath for 2 hours when a small quantity of a precipitate was obtained. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into a cooled solution of ammonium chloride and then treated with hydrochloric acid. The ethereal layer was separated, washed with water and bicarbonate solution, the ether evaporated and the residue hydrolysed with 5% methyl alcoholic caustic potash. The oily product, obtained after the addition of water, was thrice extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated. On distilling the residue, the main fraction distilled over between 167° and 175° at 3-4 mm. with a very small forerun of a more mobile liquid with a characteristic odour, which is probably the corresponding unsaturated hydrocarbon. On redistillation, the carbinol was obtained as a colourless limpid oil with a very faint odour, b p. 167°-172°/3 mm., yield 80 g. [Found: C, 79·8, 79·7; H, 13·4, 13·4; Iodine value (Wijs), 89, 87. $C_{20}H_{40}O$ requires C, 81·1; H, 13·5 per cent. Iodine value, 86].

The analytical data in this as well as in the subsequent preparations were not very satisfactory due to the fact that the oleic acid, which was the starting material, always contains other fatty acids which are very difficult to separate by fractional distillation. Nevertheless, the almost theoretical iodine value indicated that the substance was not very impure.

Methyl Δ^7 -Heptadecenoate (Methyl nor-oleate) (II).—The carbinol (30 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (250 c.c.) and a solution of bromine (5·7 c.c.) in glacial acetic acid (110 c.c.) was added drop by drop, under cooling. There was immediate decolourisation at the beginning but after the addition

of bromine was complete, a faint colour persisted. The solution was next heated on the water-bath and chromic acid mixture, prepared by dissolving 58 g. of chromic anhydride (80-85%) in 35 c.c. of warm water and diluting with 375 c.c. of acetic acid, was added in course of $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours with occasional shaking. When the addition was complete the mixture was heated for further 3 hours; some rectified spirit was added to remove excess of CrO_3 and the acetic acid removed as far as possible under reduced pressure. The residue was warmed with dilute sulphuric acid and then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water (if a slight emulsion was formed it was broken up by the addition of salt), the ether removed and the residue dried in a vacuum desiccator and weighed. It was then dissolved in 225 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, zinc dust (35 g.) added and the solution heated on the water-bath for 2 hours after which it was filtered hot. Acetic acid was then removed in *vacuo*, the residue treated with dilute sulphuric acid to decompose any zinc salt formed and the mixture extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed twice with water and then thrice with *N*-NaOH solution. The alkaline solution was concentrated and treated with salt when sodium nor-oleate salted out. This was filtered, decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution washed with water, dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated. The product (10 g.), after drying in a vacuum desiccator, was esterified with methyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 5 c.c.) by heating under reflux for 4 hours. The product was worked up as usual and then distilled and the fraction boiling between 158° — $167^\circ/6$ mm. collected. On redistillation, it boiled between 159° — 165° at 6 mm., yield 5 g. The ester readily decolourises bromine and permanganate. (Found: C, 75.5, 75.7; H, 11.5, 11.7. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.6; H, 12.0 per cent).

1: 1-Dimethyl- Δ^8 -Heptadecenol-1(III).—This was prepared from methyl nor-oleate (10 g.) and methyl magnesium iodide (from 4 g. of magnesium and 13 c.c. of methyl iodide) in a manner exactly similar to that described under the other carbinol. After the removal of the unreacted methyl nor-oleate the residue was distilled and the portion boiling between 158° — 164° at 4 mm. collected separately. On redistillation, it boiled at 160° — $164^\circ/4$ mm., yield 8 g. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 13.2. Iodine value, 91. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}$ requires C, 80.8; H, 13.5 per cent. Iodine value, 90).

Methyl Δ^6 -Hexadecenoate (IV).—1: 1-Dimethyl- Δ^8 -heptadecenol-1 (9.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) was brominated with bromine (1.8 c.c.) in glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.) and then treated with a mixture formed by dissolving chromic acid (21 g.) in warm water (18 c.c.) and then diluting

with acetic acid (130 c.c.). The oxidation mixture was worked up as before and then debrominated with zinc (9 g.) in acetic acid (80 c.c.). The debrominated acid was extracted from the ethereal solution with sodium hydroxide solution and then salted out. The sodium soap was decomposed in the usual way and the acid, after separation, was esterified with methyl alcohol and sulphuric acid. After two distillations, the ester boiled at 150° - $155^{\circ}/6$ mm. The ester decolourises bromine and permanganate solution. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 11.5. Iodine value, 96. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{32}O_2$: C, 76.1; H, 11.9 per cent. Iodine value, 95)

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Received October 5, 1930.
